

GOALS AND TASKS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCES IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *It is very important for students studying in primary education, which is the first stage of education, to master a number of competencies that are required and considered relevant in today's modern educational environment. In this regard, this article talks about the goals and tasks of developing linguistic competences in elementary school students.*

Keywords: *primary education, primary school student, linguistic competence, quality of education, independent linguistic person.*

In today's modern educational conditions, the issue of modernization of education shows its priority. In this regard, one of the conditions for improving the quality of education is the formation of a comprehensive system of basic competencies, i.e., general knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as independent activity experience, which determine the modern quality of educational content in accordance with personal responsibility. In the development of basic personal competences, attention should be paid to the first stage of education - primary education. It is appropriate to pay special attention to language education aimed at educating elementary school students as citizens of their own country, improving their knowledge, humane attitude towards others, and being demanding towards themselves of course.

In order to ensure the consistency of the content of general education subjects taught in general secondary, secondary special, vocational education based on the continuity of education in our country and the orientation towards educating a well-rounded person, 6 basic competencies and specific competencies were defined based on the content of each academic subject. Formation of these competencies starting from primary grades is the main requirement of today. In primary grades, to be able to clearly express one's opinion verbally and in writing, to be able to logically ask simple questions based on the topic, to be able to dress up, to be able to apply the knowledge gained by students in everyday life, the basic skills of self-management, behavior in a team, formation of vocabulary, adherence to cultural norms and a healthy lifestyle in behavior are formed.

Competency-based approach in education means teaching students to effectively apply various skills acquired in situations in their personal, professional and social life. It is necessary for a person to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships in his life, to take his place in society, to solve the problems he faces, and most importantly, to be a competitive staff in his field and profession. must have basic competencies.

Competence education aims not only to acquire a certain set of knowledge, but also to develop the abilities of personality development, understanding and creation. In accordance with this, the purpose of education and the priority of its content also change: the main goal of forming knowledge, skills and abilities is directed to the formation of the ability to use them freely in solving practical problems in life. Therefore, today's student should be able to apply them correctly in practice, along with acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities.

It should also be noted that the changes taking place in the social and economic spheres of modern society have created new demands on the teacher. This shows that a teacher suitable for modern educational conditions should be a specialist with a wide range of general cultural, professional and special competences, who can adequately respond to new professional requirements and working conditions. Training a professional teacher who is ready to live and work in a rapidly changing society is a strategic task facing the system of professional pedagogical education. Therefore, today, the transition to the competence paradigm of education is becoming more urgent. This relevance is also intended for students who prepare the future specialist. It is for this reason that the improvement of the competency paradigm of education among specialists who provide knowledge to primary school students, which is considered the first stage of education, proves to be relevant.

At the socio-pedagogical level, the issue of developing the competence of educational independence of elementary school students in learning their mother tongue is very important. In particular, it is important to define specific goals and tasks in the development of linguistic competences in elementary school students.

From a scientific-theoretical point of view, the importance of the goals and tasks of developing language competences in primary school students comes from the needs of primary education. In this process, it is important to attach importance to the need to develop the competence of educational independence of elementary school students, which is the basis for the formation of a competent independent linguistic personality of students of junior school age. Among the main competences of a primary school student in learning his mother tongue are language knowledge, skills, knowledge of their use, and the skills of conscious self-organization of a primary school student. The presence of competences such as language independence leads to the formation of a linguistic personality.

It is known that mother tongue education has been mainly concerned with the development of linguistic competence in students. Linguistic competence of students is their knowledge of the language, the ability to connect this knowledge with practice, and the ability to create speech. If the knowledge given to students on language construction is focused on the development of their oral and written speech, it will serve to form their linguistic competence. Knowledge that is not useful for the improvement of oral and written speech is not part of linguistic competence. In general, the money and time spent on providing linguistic knowledge that is not connected with practice and does not create speaking skills is not justified. For example, the rules of correct pronunciation of foreign words along with the knowledge of accent will develop students' speaking skills. However, the knowledge that the stress of the word falls on the last syllable in Uzbek, and that some adverbs do not receive stress at the end of the word, is not part of linguistic competence. After all, this knowledge does not become a skill. Even if the student does not have them, he will not make a mistake in stressing the syllables in the appropriate places.

In the formation of linguistic competence, the purposeful mastery of methods of action that ensure the recognition of language phenomena and their use in speech is also important.

Learning the language system is not an end in itself. In the process of formation of linguistic competence, it is important to develop the student's personality, cognitive culture, logical memory, self-evaluation and introspection skills.

In primary education, the task of educating the language personality and forming linguistic and language components in primary school students by means of the science of mother tongue

and reading literacy comes to the fore based on the cognitive function and cognitive importance of the language.

Knowledge of words is the basis of linguistic competence. The students' vocabulary serves to ensure the accuracy, correctness, fluency and variety of speech. Feeling the word means feeling the mother tongue. It is not for nothing that when comparing the works of artists, the quantity of words used by writers is not considered as one of the main evaluation criteria. Therefore, vocabulary should be the basis of mother tongue linguistic education. It is precisely this, formed in the set of didactic games, that is used in the process of the lesson, which prevents the student from getting bored of the lesson. It also allows him to improve his mobility with the help of a didactic game.

In the conditions of globalization, the clash of different cultures and the situation of national and international communication require young people to have a high communication culture and vocabulary. This requires improvement of mother tongue education, raising the acquired qualifications of students to the level of linguistic competence. For this reason, it is very important to prepare students for higher education by acquiring linguistic competence right from the primary grade.

Education competence of young people is becoming an important integral part of educational processes. It is important to lay the foundation for this from primary education. Because our students, who have abilities in various fields, are taking the first place with their skills in various competitions in the world today. Without deviating from the problem set in the label, it should be said that the issue of developing linguistic competences among primary school students is very important here. After all, every student from the existing level can show his place in the educational processes with this ability even after he goes to higher education.

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